

UNVEILING PERSPECTIVES ON PERFORMANCE RECOGNITION OF TEACHERS: A QUALITATIVE INQUIRY

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Unveiling Perspectives on Performance Recognition of Teachers: A Qualitative Inquiry

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Abstract

Performance recognition is a program implemented in school in order to recognize the performance of teachers in teaching, curricular and co-curricular activities in school. The primary objective of this study was to explore the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, insights gained by the teachers on performance recognition and how performance recognition motivate teacher to perform better. The study was conducted in four schools in Laak South District, Davao de Oro. A qualitative phenomenological research design was employed, and purposive sampling was utilized to select eight participants. The study's findings revealed that participants' experiences in receiving and qualifying for performance recognition were: felt validated, pressured, not easy but doable, awarded at the start of the pandemic, teachers perform in various aspects, and stressful yet challenging. The challenges they encountered were overlapping tasks, disciplining the students, and sacrificing sleep. Their coping mechanisms were proper time management, asking assistance from colleagues, encouraging learners, prioritizing tasks, applying previous knowledge, getting to know the learners, and being open on their emotions. The paper concluded with the recommendation that the findings from teachers' experiences will assist the school administrators in improving the performance recognition program implemented in respective schools.

Keywords: *performance recognition, lived-experiences, coping mechanisms, insights gained, motivation*

Introduction

The act of receiving recognition for one's actions often instills a sense of worth and significance in individuals. Within the educational context, it is a prevailing circumstance that the majority of teachers do not receive recognition or compensation for the extensive amount of time they dedicate to meticulously planning and organizing instructional materials and activities for their students (Andrews, 2011). This resulted in teachers being unmotivated, reduced productivity, and job satisfaction in their work.

Receiving performance recognition can boost both loyalty and productivity. Movsessian (2018) revealed that teachers at ABC School in Los Angeles, California, want performance recognition for increased test scores, student performance, improvements made to the school, and so on. Since these systems do not exist on campus, teachers felt that school leaders needed to recognize their work. Based on the findings obtained from interviews and a survey, it has been ascertained that teachers prefer private recognition that occurs outside the presence of others on campus since this type of recognition reinforces their activities. Furthermore, the educators at ABC School actively pursue financial incentives and career advancements, acknowledging the inherent challenges associated with obtaining such rewards within the educational framework.

The Philippines has established a National Teacher Recognition Program (NTRP) to acknowledge exceptional educators. The program encompasses yearly Teacher of the Year awards, commendation for exceptional performance in specific topic domains, distinctive prizes for inventive pedagogical approaches, community engagement honors, and long-standing service recognitions (Public School Teacher Rewards and Recognition Act, 2023). Nevertheless, the program's efficacy in tackling issues related to performance recognition has yet to be well-researched.

In relation to teacher recognition program, the secondary schools in Laak South District have established a school-based performance recognition program. Each month, teachers are selected to receive the title of Most Performing Teacher of the Month. At the end of the school year, one teacher will be awarded the title of Most Performing Teacher of the Year. Certain criteria, such as the teacher's punctuality and submission of special reports and etc., are considered to determine the most effective teacher. Despite the implementation of this school-based performance recognition program, there is no research-based in data as to the proper assessments of teachers lived-experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, insights gained in performance recognition and how it motivates the teachers to perform better.

This study, therefore, seeks to unveil the experiences of teachers in qualifying performance recognition to extract the meaning of performance recognition in the lives of teachers. Hence, the researcher would like to embark on the study and explore the lived experiences of teachers regarding performance recognition implemented in their school. Further, the result of this study may inform the Department of Education on the current situation and problems of teachers through their experiences and challenges encountered that could hinder them provide quality education to the learners and provide effective solutions to solve the problem. Also, this can provide relevant information and suggestions that would possibly help the school administration to improve the school-based recognition program implemented.

Research Questions

The study aimed to explore the perspectives of the participants on the performance recognition in their respective schools. This was

guided by the following questions.

1. What are the lived experiences of teachers in receiving and qualifying on performance recognition?
2. How does performance recognition motivate the teacher to perform better?
3. What are the challenges faced by teachers in receiving performance recognition?
4. What are the coping mechanisms used by the teachers in dealing with the challenges encountered in achieving the performance recognition?
5. What are the insights gained by the teachers from their experiences in performance recognition?

Literature Review

Performance Recognition of Teachers

The research identifies several elements that influence the effectiveness of performance recognition for teachers. Factors such as empowerment, organizational communication, work-life balance, and recognition and rewards have a substantial impact on improving teacher effectiveness (Jain, 2023).

A study in Junior High School teachers at Babat Supat District, Indonesia with 100 teachers as respondents, found that: (1) there was a relationship between reward and teachers performance at state junior high schools in the Babat Supat District; (2) there was a relationship between achievement motivation and teachers' performance at state junior high schools in the Babat Supat District; and (3) there was a relationship between reward and achievement motivation simultaneously (Ningsih et al., 2021). Hence, high-performing teachers always strive to complete all tasks given to them appropriately and in accordance with their talents in order to produce the best possible work outcomes.

Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE)

Performance recognition refers to the acknowledgment and appreciation of an individual's achievements and accomplishments in their work or professional setting and to recognize that there are various recognition practices implemented in schools. Recognition practices in teaching vary across different fields and disciplines.

The Department of Education established Programs on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE) to encourage, recognize and reward employees, individually or in groups for their suggestions, innovative ideas, inventions, discoveries, superior accomplishments that contribute to efficacy, and improvement in government operations which lead to organizational productivity (Deped Order no 9, s. 2002). Thus, providing incentives and awards based on exemplary performance, innovative ideas and exemplary behavior has been observed.

According to the study of David (2023), on the attitude of teachers towards DepEd Awards' Mechanisms in public secondary schools of Division of Antique, teachers rated DepEd awards as "Favorable" regarding job growth, personal pleasure, social recognition, and monetary fulfillment, with a mean score of 4.44. Teachers' opinions towards DepEd awards differed based on gender, age, most excellent educational level, and teaching position. They valued professional advancement, personal fulfillment, social recognition, and monetary gratification.

Experiences of Teachers in Receiving Performance Recognition

Teaching as a noble profession need to be rewarded by both financial and non-financial means. But, the study of Bawalla and Yakub (2018) on the rewards enjoyed by the teachers in Ogun State, Nigeria from the government, it showed that teachers see their monthly salaries as the only reward granted to them. They believed that there are other allowances that motivate workers perhaps than monthly salaries. The financial allowances, like housing allowances, transport allowances, medical, and welfares should be offered if job commitment is to be enhanced. Because of this, teachers were not satisfied with their pay and are not motivated by the rewards in which the state played prominent role in agitating for good wages and working conditions for teachers.

Performance-based rewards are consistently included in the educational system of the Philippines. Despite the considerable problems surrounding it, the government continues developing various prizes, bonuses, or incentives to enhance staff motivation. The research conducted by Cordovilla and Dela Cruz (2021) unveiled how participants encountered difficulties with the adherence requirements for the allocation of PBB. The criteria are derived from Deped Order No. 12 s. 2013 and encompass the liquidated MOOE reports, NAT results, drop-out rate, enrolment number, promotions per school year, and the RPMS. Consequently, following these specific criteria/guidelines led to heightened stress levels due to the program's implementation, necessitating teachers to work longer and more hours.

Barends et al. (2022) stated that when employees receive recognition, they feel validated, leading to numerous positive outcomes. Validation through performance recognition can enhance job satisfaction, motivation and over-all well-being. It affirms employees' efforts making them feel valued and respected, which can enhance their commitment and productivity. Studies suggest that non-financial rewards, such as verbal praise and acknowledgment, are particularly effective in fostering a sense of validation and improving employee morale and engagement.

Challenges of Teachers Receiving Performance Recognition

Teachers face several challenges when it comes to receiving performance recognition. The study conducted by Stephen (2023) found that Performance-Based Rewards have varying effects on teachers' performance. It revealed that PBR serves as a motivating factor for teachers, leading to increased performance, enhanced productivity, and improved efficiency. However, this method promotes competition instead of collaboration and undermines the concept of a collegiate approach in productive schools, suppressing conflict and tension in the school environment.

Additionally, Aslam (2011), argued that the use of unreliable metrics for assessing teacher performance hinders the fair recognition of teachers. In developing countries like Pakistan, factors such as decreased motivation for evaluation, least participation in decision making, and lack of training for evaluating performance further contribute to the challenges of recognizing teachers for their performance (Oltedal, 2018). These challenges highlight the need for local empirical research and context-specific reforms to improve recognition and reward systems for teachers.

Moreover, Kituyi et. al (2014), reveal that delays in release of the tokens are a major challenge to the school-based reward system. Most teachers felt the principals held on to the tokens until it was too late in the year thus suggested that a specific body comprising certain teachers be set up to manage the school – based reward systems' fund so as to minimize wrangles among teachers as well as delays in releasing of the funds by certain principals. Also, some teachers felt that the reward systems were not wholly embracive or inclusive enough to reward all efforts put in by teachers. Some teachers for instance claimed to have stayed in schools much longer than the rest of the teachers guiding, counseling and helping students change their attitudes but such kind of efforts seemed neither to be recognized nor rewarded.

Motivation on Performance Recognition

Motivation is a pivotal factor that significantly impacts an individual's performance within a professional environment. Work motivation is influenced by several elements, such as leadership, work environment, training, task characteristics, rewards, career route, and dedication (Mohammad et al., 2023). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are two types of motivation, with intrinsic motivation having a powerful impact on improving productivity (Alina & Ion, 2023). Studies demonstrate a substantial correlation between motivation and employee performance, wherein both financial and non-financial incentives play crucial roles in enhancing corporate productivity and elevating staff morale (Sourav, 2023). Performance recognition greatly impact motivation of employees.

Coping Mechanisms of Teachers in Performance Recognition

Teachers use a variety of coping mechanisms to deal with the stress of being evaluated. These include positive coping strategies such as spending time with family members (Minz, 2023), engaging in enjoyable activities (Javed, Rehman & Shehzadi, 2022), and turning to religion (Hui et al., 2022). Problem-solving coping strategies, such as seeking social support and actively solving the problem, are also commonly used (Otilia, 2018).

Teachers employ several coping strategies to handle the acknowledgment of their performance and its impact on their overall well-being. Studies suggest that positive reframing, active coping, planning, open communication, realistic expectations, exposure therapy, and deep breathing are highly beneficial tactics utilized by teachers (Rajesh, 2022). These coping strategies assist educators in managing the challenges linked to performance assessment, anxiety, and stress, enhancing their mental well-being and job contentment. In addition, the study emphasizes the significance of including coping mechanisms in teaching methods to enhance teacher resilience and reduce emotional exhaustion, particularly as teaching tenure progresses (Bragina, 2023). Teachers can improve their ability to handle performance recognition issues and protect their overall well-being in educational environments by acknowledging and employing these coping techniques.

Insights Gained in Performance Recognition

Recognizing teacher performance involves several insights. The purpose of performance-based incentive programs in schools should be to ensure that teachers are regarded as the key players in the school's administrative and academic aspects. Additionally, administrators need to be educated on the importance of performance-based reward programs and aware that compensation encourages instructors to provide their best effort (Stephen, 2023)

According to Lindsay et al. (2002), a well-designed staff appraisal system can provide valuable professional development for teachers and enable school management to assess teachers' performance. Educators have conveyed a strong inclination towards receiving acknowledgment for their work performance, underscoring the significance of recognition in enhancing their overall work performance and fostering their professional growth. This implies that acknowledging and acknowledging the performance of teachers can serve as a viable and streamlined approach for school administrators to augment teacher performance.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research approach specifically the phenomenological design. A qualitative phenomenological research

design seeks to discover what a certain experience means to a group of people and how they experienced it (Goulding, 2005). Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) is a participant-oriented approach that enables participants to thoroughly articulate their lived experiences at a profound or in-depth level.

Participants

The researcher selected eight teachers, two teachers per school from four secondary schools in Laak South District through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling, also known as judgment sampling, involves selecting participants based explicitly on their attributes. This nonrandom technique does not require a predetermined number of participants or underlying hypotheses. In other words, the researcher determines what information is required and then searches for sources willing and able to provide it based on their expertise or experience. This sampling technique is often used when researchers want to study a specific population or phenomenon in-depth.

The criteria in selecting the participants are as follows: a.) a public-school teacher assigned in Laak South District; b.) at least three years in service; c.) received a performance recognition; d) must be communicative and willing to participate. The researcher has selected eight participants to conduct the in-depth interview (IDI).

Procedure

In collecting the data, the following steps was observed. A letter was sent to the Division Superintendent to ask permission for the conduct of the study. After the interview guide has been validated, the researcher secured ethics form for ethics review committee clearance. The approved letter from the Division Superintendent was attached to the letter sent to the school heads of the identified schools to request approval for the conduct of the in-depth interview. The collection of data through an in-depth in person interview with selected informants was conducted. The interview questions were in English however research participants were allowed to answer the questions in English, Filipino or Bisaya. There were two interview sessions, the other one was for follow-up and it lasted for 15-30 minutes each session. Consent form was sent to each of the eight teachers and all informants were asked to attach their signature therein. After the interview of the informants, the data was then encoded, thematized, analyzed and interpreted to address the research objectives. The transcripts were double-checked by the researcher to ensure the authenticity of the data.

Data Analysis

To analyze the results of the data gathered from the in-depth interview, the researcher used the Thematic Analysis, since the purpose of this study was to explore the perspectives, experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms and insights gained of teachers on performance recognition practices.

Thematic Analysis as described by Braun and Clarke (2013) allowed a systematic way of seeing, as well as processing qualitative information using “coding”. This specific method in analyzing qualitative data had six phases which includes data familiarization, generating code, constructing themes, reviewing potential themes, defining and naming themes and producing the report.

The first phase, data familiarization involved transcribing the data, re-reading the data, and noting down the initial ideas. Major ideas were highlighted and written down for each transcript.

The second phase, generating codes, involved generating of initial codes. Researchers identified and label notable features of data systematically.

The third phase, constructing themes, researchers sorted the codes into potential codes. This involved grouping related codes and identified the emerging themes out of the responses of the participants.

The fourth phase, reviewing potential themes, involved refining identified themes. Researcher checked if themes worked in relation to coded extracts. Revisions were done based on the suggestions of the informants in the in-depth interview

The fifth stage, defining and naming themes, researchers defined the essence of each theme and sub-theme, providing clear names and descriptions that encapsulate their meanings.

Lastly, producing the report, involved writing up the analysis, presenting the themes supported by relevant data extracts. Data collected were analyzed by the data analyst to ensure the validity of the reported result.

Ethical Considerations

It was the researcher's duty to respect the respondents' rights, needs, values, and preferences prior to conducting the study. The researcher had taken the required steps to carefully abide by the ethical standards in order to protect the participants' identity, confidentiality, dignity, and rights. The researcher was therefore carefully follow the following guidelines when acquiring the data (Mirza et al., 2023).

Ethic of Respect. Everyone who participated in the research was treated with respect and complete trust. Regardless of age, sex, color, religion, political convictions, way of life, or any other significant difference between the participants and the researchers, every study conducted with respect for the participants.

Relationship with Participants and Conflict of Interest. The researcher was built an open and transparent relationship with each participant throughout the many research phases. The researcher distinguished between their friendships and professional relationships with them and their relationships as research participants.

Informed Consent. Before commencing the study, the researcher ascertained that all participants have provided informed permission as a prerequisite for their involvement. Consequently, the informed consent was distributed a week before the in-depth interview. Participants were requested to engage in extra reading to acquire further information and enhance their comprehension regarding their involvement in the study. The participants were free to choose whether to engage in the study.

Moreover, it was the researcher's responsibility to ensure that the participants in this study were entirely voluntary and not coerced into participation.

Confidentiality and Anonymity. The researcher protected the anonymity of the research participants and the privacy of the collected data. Participants are given pseudonyms to maintain their confidentiality and privacy. The researcher made sure to the participants that the information were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the findings to the research questions that explored the perspectives on performance recognition from the viewpoints of teachers. The primary focus of the investigation was on the experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms of teachers on performance recognition. The research participants were purposively selected from the four secondary schools, two teachers per school, in Laak South District.

Using the following criteria a.) a public-school teacher assigned in Laak South District; b.) at least three years in service; c.) received a performance recognition; d) must be communicative and willing to participate. The researcher had selected eight participants, two teachers per school to undergo the in-depth interview (IDI).

The responses were subjected to content analysis where the themes across all responses were drawn. In keeping with the research ethics for qualitative research, codes had been used in order to conceal the identities of the research participants. The presentation of the result was done according to the order of specific research questions used in this study.

Theme 1: Experiences in Receiving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition.

The themes in this section were coming from the specific research question 1 'What are the lived-experiences of teachers on the performance recognition?' The responses generated the following themes: felt validated, pressured, and stressful yet challenging.

Subtheme 1: Felt Validated

This theme constituted the primary response to the experiences of teachers in receiving and qualifying performance recognition. It meant that performance recognition made the performance of teachers were validated. Informant emphasized that receiving performance recognition made people think that you are really performing your job as a teacher. Informant 7 pointed out;

As a teacher receiving and qualifying performance recognition in school, my experiences may include: validation of efforts- I felt validated and appreciated for my hard work, dedication, and contributions to student's learning and the school community.

Subtheme 3: Pressured

Some teachers experienced pressure in qualifying the performance recognition. They were pressured in managing their time in doing their classes and complying the needed reports at the same time. This statement is supported by informant 1 as she claimed;

Experiences? Pressured. Pressured sa time kay compliance, magklase, unya naa kay e comply today, so murag multitasking siya.

(Experiences? Pressured. Pressured on time of compliance and in teaching, it became multitasking.)

Subtheme 3: Stressful Yet Challenging

The research informants viewed in qualifying performance recognition as stressful yet challenging one. It captures the essence of the situations or experiences that are demanding but also present opportunities for growth and development. Informant shared;

First and foremost, stressful siya pero challenging. Challenging in a sense na naa kay target goal nga kailangan pero dili najud yun ana, ako competitive man ko pero dili jud sa yun ana ka lala kay guided naman ka sa indicators. So, as a department head naa koy counter-responsibility sa pagdisiplina sa mga bata kay ang performance in general nila will affect to my performance. So, pag mag rank 1 ko apil sila sa contributor sa akoang achievement.

(First and foremost, it was stressful but challenging. Challenging in a sense that you have your target goal but not as hard as that because you are guided with the indicators. So, as a department head I have a counter-responsibility in disciplining the students because in general their performance will affect mine. So, when I will be rank 1 they are the contributor for that achievement.)

Theme 2: Ways Experiences Affect One's Motivation to Perform

This section presents the results to the 2nd major research question 'How does performance recognition motivate the teacher to perform better?' Data collected for this question highlighting how performance recognition motivate teachers to perform better in their respective duties.

Subtheme 1: Motivated to Perform Well

Being motivated to perform well generally involves having a strong reason to achieve and excel in tasks given to a particular person. This drive can be fueled by intrinsic and extrinsic factors. As informant 5 had this to say;

It motivates me to perform well, trabaho, mag sayo sa tanang mga buluhaton dili lang mu break sa deadline kundi kung kaya na trabahoon karun ang mga reports trabahoon na. maka motivate sa akoo para magtrabaho ug tarong.

(It motivates me to perform well, work, being early in submitting the reports, do not just break the deadline but submit earlier than the deadline. It motivates me to work well.)

Performance recognition serve as powerful motivator for the teacher as validation of their efforts and work. Informant 7 stated;

Performance recognition serves as a powerful motivator for me as a teacher by providing validation of my efforts, fostering a sense of accomplishment, increasing morale and engagement, and making a positive impact on my student's learning and success.

Subtheme 2: Eager to Work for Recognition

As the result showed, teachers motivated by recognition put a significant effort and strive for high performance. This can lead to enhanced productivity and quality of work.

Mas eager ko mo trabaho because ma recognize ug para ma recognize ka.

(I am more eager to work to be recognized.)

Theme 3: Specific Difficulties Encountered in Achieving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition

This section presents the results on the challenges of the research participants of just to qualify and received the performance recognition. This was the gist of the 3rd major research question, 'What are the challenges faced by teachers in performance recognition?'

Subtheme 1: Overlapping Tasks

This theme emphasized on the overlapping task or reports of teachers just to be qualified for the performance recognition. This could happen when the school principal asked for immediate reports need to be submitted. Informant 1 narrated;

Pag multitask, sapaw sapaw na trabaho to the point nga dapat magklase nag finish ka sa imohang report sa classroom. (Multitasking, there are overlapping of tasks to the point that you do the reports needed to submit inside the classroom instead of having class.)

Subtheme 2: Disciplining the Students

Teachers find it challenging to discipline the students since their performance affect the performance of the teacher. Informant 7 stated;

The specific difficulties I encountered in achieving and qualifying for performance recognition included questioning whether I truly remained an effective teacher for the upcoming school years, especially amidst current difficulties in disciplining students' behavior.

Subtheme 3: Sacrificing Sleep

To meet the demands or achieve the goals needs a sacrifice sleep is a common practice of teachers who are aiming for performance recognition. Informant 6 stated;

In contests, need jud siya ug time unya naay mga instances nga mag sacrifice jud ka, need kag time para maka focus ka sa contest nga imohang apilan. Kasi sa amin we are participating as teacher's category so kami talaga ang sasalang hindi bata so need talaga mag prepare. There are some instances nga imohang sleep is ma sacrifice jud siya. Matulog kag dugay, mata kag sayo kay alas 6 sa buntag contest na. Mag invest jud kag time and effort. (In contests, there are instances that you need to sacrifice, you need time to focus on the contest. We are participating as teacher participants not the students. So, we need ample time to prepare. There are some instances that we need to sacrifice our sleep. We go to bed late and we need to wake up at 6:00 in the morning for the contest. You really need to invest time and effort.)

Theme 4: Coping Mechanisms Used to Address Challenges

The themes created in this section were from the responses to the research question 4, 'What are the coping mechanisms used by the teachers in dealing with the challenges encountered in achieving the performance recognition?' The themes were embedded with proper time management, ask assistant from colleagues, and encourage learners.

Subtheme 1: Proper Time Management

The result showed maximizing productivity and achieving goals efficiently requires proper time management. Teachers coped with those challenges encountered by having a proper time management to perform their respective task.

Informant 4 narrated how he coped with those challenges he encountered;

The coping mechanism that I did to address those challenge is really finding a time management strategy that works best in my personality, self-discipline and of course self-motivation. I also practice setting priorities, first ginauna sa gyud ug buhat ang pinakadapat nga urgent nga humanon. Another one, is dapat well organized gyud sa mga buhaton that is why I always keep organized most specifically in scheduling time appropriately such as doing time log and protecting my time from interruptions.

(The coping mechanism that I did to address those challenge is really finding a time management strategy that works best in my personality, self-discipline and of course self-motivation. I also practice setting priorities, first I do first the urgent one that need to be done. Another one, is you should be organized in everything you do that is why I always keep organized most specifically in scheduling time appropriately such as doing time log and protecting my time from interruptions.)

Subtheme 2: Ask Assistance from Colleagues

Another coping mechanism of teachers was asking for some help from other teachers. This was one of the helpful ways to solve the problems encountered especially inside the classroom in terms of disciplining the students. Informant 3 shared;

Mag ask jud ug assistance jud maam gikan sa ubang teachers ug sa mga seasoned teachers labi sa pag disiplina sa mga bata kay mas naa baya silay experience since dugay na sila sa serbisyo.

(I ask assistance from the other teachers and to the seasoned one especially in disciplining the students because they are more experienced more than me.)

Subtheme 3: Encourage Learners

The concept of encouraging learners was essential for fostering motivation, engagement and a positive learning environment. This way, students are motivated to perform better and learners will be empowered to reach their full potential. Informant 2 cited;

Constant reminders sa mga estudyante, follow-up jud pirmente. Always jud sila e check, eencourage ug e motivate. During recognition e acknowledge pod nimo sila para ganahan sila. For example, sa WATCH Award naa man sila madawat na certificates noh apil man pod na siya sa indicators nagahatag jud ko sa ilahag plus points mag WATCH Awardee sila.

(Constant reminders and follow-up on students. Always check them, encourage and motivate. During recognition you should acknowledge them also. For example, when they will receive a WATCH award I gave them also plus points to their quizzes or on their performance tasks.)

Theme 5: Insights Gained from Experiences as a Teacher on Receiving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition

The results in this section were taken from the responses to the research question 5, 'What are the insights gained by the teachers from their experiences on performance recognition?' The following were the themes drawn from the responses; performance recognition as a good program, provide good influence, and build positive relationship with students.

Subtheme 1: Performance Recognition as a Good Program

Performance recognition programs can be highly beneficial for organizations as they promote a positive work culture, motivate employees and drive productivity. Informant emphasized how good this program when school heads are true to their promised incentives. Informant 5 emphasized how good this program when school heads are true to their promised incentives.

Maayo gyud ning yung ani nga program sa school ang dili lang maayo kanang naay mga saad ang school head or principal nga mga incentives unya wala jud natupad. So, akong nakat onan ana di lang siguro ta mupalabi ug asa noh, mutrabaho lang gihapon bisan naay yun ana nga panghitabo.

(It is truly a good program; what is not good is that there are school heads who do not keep their promises in terms of giving of incentives. So, I learned that we should not hope too much, work accordingly despite that.)

Subtheme 2: Provide Good Influence

Another insight from participant was performance recognition provides a good influence to teachers and students. It has a vital role in influencing their performance and dedication to their work. Informant 4 shared;

For me, teachers have a vital role in determining the direction of our society, thus schools must continue to emphasize how important it is to acknowledge and value them. I believe that giving teachers recognition naghatag gyud ug dakung impluwensya (it gives a big influence) on their performance and engagement, dili lamang (not just) to just making them feel good about themselves. Therefore,

educators may change their schools and improve the lives of both teachers and students by praising hard work and providing timely praise.

Subtheme 3: Build Positive Relationship with the Students

Another participant stressed on building a positive relationship with the students as her insight in qualifying the performance recognition. Informant 7 said;

The valuable insight from my experiences is recognizing the significance of building positive relationships with students as the foundation for effective teaching and behavioral management and understanding the need for flexibility and adaptability in my teaching approach to accommodate diverse student needs and address behavioral challenges effectively.

The structured themes and the emerging therein were made as bases in broadening the discussion of the findings. As each theme was connected to related literature and studies, they were subjected to a thorough review and assessment to determine their consistency with the theme.

The study was focused on the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms and insights gained by the eight teachers from four schools in the Laak South District on receiving and qualifying to performance recognition. The research participants were in the age of 25-45 years of age, 25% were males while 75% were females, with three years and above in the service. They have received various performance recognition (e.g. Most Performing Teacher) in various aspects within and beyond traditional teaching duties.

Experiences in Receiving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition. The emerging themes in this structured theme are felt validated, pressured and stressful yet challenging.

The finding revealed that teachers felt validated when they received and qualified for performance recognition. They felt that all their efforts were being faded off, valued, and appreciated by the school administration, colleagues, students, and parents when they were awarded as a performing teacher. Barends et al. (2022) stated that when employees receive recognition, they feel validated, leading to numerous positive outcomes. This implied that validation through performance recognition can enhance job satisfaction, motivation, and overall well-being of teachers. It affirms their efforts, making them feel valued and respected, which can enhance their commitment and productivity.

Moreover, being pressured and feeling stressed in complying with the needed reports just to be qualified to be a performing one and to maintain the image top were some of the participants' experiences. Some teachers experienced pressure and stress in qualifying for performance recognition. They were pressured to manage their time in doing their classes and stress complying with the needed reports simultaneously. According to a study of Priya, et.al (2023), that examined the effects of target pressure and performance on corporate employees' psychological health. It was shown that although the pressure to perform well might inspire workers if taken the wrong way, it can also result in stress and a decline in well-being. An inverted U-shaped curve represents the relationship between performance pressure and employee vigor/dedication, suggesting that while moderate pressure can improve performance, extreme pressure can have the opposite effect. It can be explained that due to pressure teachers cannot balanced their teaching, report submission and other school activities.

Ways the Performance Recognition Motivate One to Perform Better. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: motivated to perform well and eager to do work for recognition. The finding revealed that performance recognition motivated the teachers to perform well as teachers with their corresponding duties and responsibilities. When a teacher is motivated, she/he is also eager to work for the recognition he/she will receive afterward. The dedication of teachers is strongly correlated with their motivation. A strong level of inherent motivation is linked to a more robust professional identity and dedication to their students and the educational institution. Dedicated educators are more inclined to actively participate in their responsibilities, exhibit allegiance to their educational institutions, and devote themselves to the learning and growth of their pupils (Ma, 2022). It is necessary that school administration should strengthen performance recognition and take it as significant orientation for employees' effective performance in school and other school-related activities.

Specific Difficulties Encountered in Achieving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition. Informants share their specific difficulties encountered in achieving and qualifying the performance recognition. The emerging themes are: overlapping tasks, disciplining students and sacrificing sleep.

Multitasking was part of the teacher's everyday life. Informants shared their challenges, and one of them was the overlapping task. Because of the overlapping reports that must be submitted, they must multitask to comply with the indicators of being a performing teacher. This is mainly why their teaching career was disturbed; they are more focused on complying with the reports. The presence of overlapping responsibilities adds complexity to time management, posing a challenge for teachers to effectively assign adequate time to each obligation. Inadequate time management can result in hurried classes and insufficient preparation, which can have a detrimental effect on student learning outcomes (Pepito, et.al, 2024). This causes teachers multitasking difficulties, affecting many aspects of their lives, including time management, task prioritization, and personal development.

Another difficulty is disciplining students. Discipline is teaching others to follow rules or norms by using punishment to correct undesirable behavior. A teacher uses discipline in the classroom to maintain routine, enforce school rules, and provide a safe learning environment for students. Innocent and Andala (2021) pointed out a positive correlation between good student discipline and improved academic success. This emphasis is expected to improve their academic performance since they are less prone to distractions caused by disciplinary problems and more actively involved in educational endeavors. Teachers encountered difficulty in disciplining their students when it comes to the consistency of their behaviors and being competitive in a healthy way in terms of their performance.

Sacrificing sleep to qualify for performance recognition is a common but often harmful strategy used by informants who want to meet high standards and be recognized in their workplaces. Teachers need to sacrifice sleep to prepare for the contest they would join as one of the bases to be qualified for the performance recognition. Lack of sleep can result in heightened irritation, mood fluctuations, and elevated levels of stress, all of which have negative effects in a classroom environment where emotional control is crucial for addressing the different needs of students. Well-rested teachers are more capable of managing stress and maintaining a healthy learning environment, while sleep-deprived teachers may experience burnout and decreased job satisfaction (Dubey, 2024). Teachers cannot function well on their duties when they are deprived by proper sleep and over-all productivity will be affected.

Coping Mechanism Used to Address Challenges. Informants have shared how they cope with the challenges encountered on achieving and qualifying performance recognition. Out of their responses seven responses were drawn out. These are proper time management, ask assistance from colleagues, and encourage learners.

When teachers are bombarded with overlapping reports and tasks, they use proper time management to address this challenge. Informants find a time management strategy that works best for them. In this way, they could avoid cramming, which would be less stressful. Likewise, along with time management, they would also apply self-discipline and prioritize important tasks. It talks about selecting and focusing on the most important or urgent tasks, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently and goals are achieved promptly. In this manner, they can perform their tasks efficiently and effectively.

Another coping mechanism used by the informant is asking for assistance from colleagues. They would solicit strategies from seasoned teachers, more experienced teachers, especially disciplining students. Employees can leverage the team's collective knowledge and talents by asking for help from one another. This enables them to solve problems faster, prevent duplication of effort, and guarantee that the most qualified individuals work on the appropriate projects (Lodwick, 2023). Expertise from the more experienced teachers would be a great coping mechanism for teachers who do not have enough knowledge needed to perform their job as teachers.

In addressing behavioral issues among students, informants have used getting to know the learners and constant reminders to them as coping mechanisms. Building good relationships with the students by investing time in building positive relationships based on trust, respect, and empathy can help mitigate behavioral issues and promote a sense of belonging and engagement. Also, for learners to be motivated, constant reminders and acknowledging their good performance are helpful for teachers.

Insights Gained from Experiences as a Teacher on Receiving and Qualifying the Performance Recognition. The following themes were drawn: performance recognition as a good program, provide good influence and build positive relationship with the students.

The lesson learned from the informant's performance recognition was a good program to boosts self-confidence, and they become a good influence to others if they were recognized. Performance recognition is a good motivation scheme that genuinely boosts the morale and motivation of the teachers. By receiving the award, they became a role model and a good influence on their colleagues to perform better on their tasks. Teachers stressed the value of being recognized for their efforts. They felt that receiving acknowledgment would help them advance professionally, become a role model and improved overall work performance (Lindsay, 2022).

The informant also recognizes the significance of building positive relationships with students as the foundation for effective teaching and behavioral management and understands the need for flexibility and adaptability in teaching approaches to accommodate diverse student needs and address behavioral challenges effectively.

Conclusions

The investigation's main focus was teachers' lived experiences on performance recognition. This highlighted the understanding of the teachers' experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights. Different experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights were explored and unveiled based on the data gathered.

The results showed that teachers in Laak South District faced many problems in qualifying and achieving performance recognition along the way. The participants revealed that overlapping tasks and reports hindered their primary job: teaching the students properly. They needed help balancing their time for teaching, complying with the necessary reports, and time for their families. Also, too many indicators pressured and gave them stress. For them, this should be just an extra task, not merely their main focus as teachers.

Performance recognition is a good motivation scheme for teachers because it boosts their morale and makes them feel that their efforts are valued and appreciated. They are eager to excel and perform more in their respective responsibilities. Still, if school administrations are not consistent in their implementation, there will be delayed awarding and not keeping their promises in terms of providing

incentives. In that case, the teachers might not take the program seriously.

In furtherance, the research findings from teachers' experiences and suggestions on performance recognition will assist and inform the school administration on the effectiveness of the program they have implemented. Also, through this, they could improve the program for its betterment by considering their suggestions.

Lastly, the Department of Education must take decisive action in submitting reports and other overlapping tasks. They may have a DepEd order removing administrative tasks from teachers, but they should make sure that these will be truly implemented in the school setting so that teachers can focus on the core function of teaching.

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